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Economic analysis of carbon sequestration measures

ABSTRACT

An economic assessment of a number of the carbon sequestration measures was undertaken based on cost-effectiveness criteria. The cost of each measure was assessed at EU scale and for a number of countries (Republic of Ireland, Germany, Norway and Czech Republic) where full cost data was available. Cost results are presented on a per hectare average basis and on an aggregate basis (accounting for relevant areas of implementation). Cost estimates were applied to carbon sequestration potentials derived through the project to generate a cost-effectiveness estimate (€ per mega gram of CO₂e sequestered) for each measure. At the EU scale, results indicate that a limited number of measures meet the cost-effectiveness criteria based on a shadow price of carbon of €89 CO₂e⁻¹ per megagram. The cost-effective measures at the EU scale were silvopasture, alley-cropping and hedges on both grass and cropland. A similar finding prevailed across the countries examined; however, the cost-effectiveness rankings did not remain consistent as the cost of certain measures varied across countries, which impacted cost-effectiveness.

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Part IV-General assumptions

The European Union (EU) is the main focus basis and focus around the assumptions used in this section. However, full relevant data sets were secured for the Republic of Ireland, Germany, the Czech Republic and Norway. The data sources used the EU and these countries are outlined in Tables 1 and 2.

The costs and benefits are evaluated using 2022 prices. We consider a 25-year time span for all measures (except for biochar where 100-year time span was considered) to allow for comparison and consider the full life span of the measures yielding benefits in the long run. We calculate the net present value (NPV) for each measure using the following formula (OECD, 2018):

$$NPV = (Cost_i - Benefit_i) * (1 + r)^{-t}$$

Where i is the measure considered, t is the time, and r is a discount rate set at 5%, as seen in previous studies (Toivonen and Tahvanainen, 1998; Clancy et al., 2009).

Labour cost was assumed to follow the hourly minimum wage. We use the area (Eurostat, 2023a) and price (Eurostat, 2023b) of each crop considered for crop outputs.

When measures include cropland, we use a coefficient system to account for the diversity of European crop production. Based on crop production data (Eurostat, 2023a), we allocate a weighting coefficient for the six most frequently produced crops in the EU-27. These represents 87% of the area under crop production in the country (wheat, barley, maize, oats, potatoes and oilseed rape)¹. The weights are calculated depending on the relative importance of each crop in terms of area cultivated compared to the total area of cereals, industrial crops, pulses, protein crops and root crops, such that:

$$Coefficient_i = share_i / (share_{wheat} + share_{barley} + share_{oats} + share_{oilseeds} + share_{potatoes} + share_{maize})$$

$$with\ share_i = area_i / (area_{cereal} + area_{industrial\ crops} + area_{pulses} + area_{root\ crops})$$

Where i is the crop considered.

¹ Similar approach was adopted for country-level analysis however some countries such as Ireland and Norway may have five dominant crops instead of six.

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When measures include cropland or grassland, we use input rates recommendations from Teagasc (Collins and Phelan, 2022) and apply the average European price for each input. We use data from the International Fertilizer Association (IFA, 2022) for fertiliser use. Input prices were taken from Eurostat (2023c). For input prices that were only available as indices on Eurostat, we used the Irish price to derive the other countries' prices from their index (Eurostat, 2023d).

For tillage operations, fuel requirements were taken from Teagasc advisory work (Hickey, 2013), while labour requirements for ploughing were taken from Forristal and Murphy (2009). For cropland, we consider the cost and benefit categories to be the same over the life span of the measures.

For woody-vegetation activities (alleycropping, silvopasture and hedges), we assume the costs only occur in year 1, except for tree maintenance, which occurs yearly. The cost of goods needed for tree planting are taken from Eurostat (2023e, 2021). Eurostat data on these inputs include trees, tree plants, forest tree seeds, energy, lubricants, fertilisers, soil improvers, plant protection and pesticides. For EU-27 countries, the data was divided by the forest area. The average was taken², and prices were corrected for inflation as Eurostat data are only available until 2020.

Service and labour costs are aggregated in Eurostat data, so we cannot exclude harvesting costs from them. Hence, labour requirements associated with tree planting are taken from the COFORD Council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) report (Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022).

When considering afforestation on either cropland or grassland, we take an average of the requirements of two tree species (conifer and broadleaf soft) and break down the labour requirements into categories. Labour costs for afforestation include cultivation and drainage, planting, fertilising, fencing, administration, machinery and maintenance.

Table 1 presents the main data sources for the different components associated with the carbon sequestration measures examined. Table 2 presents the key assumptions for crops, grass and forestry requirements that are used across the different measures.

² Average of 14 countries for which data were available on Eurostat. 2020 prices corrected for inflation.

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Table 1: Data sources

Sector	Sub-categories	Data Source (EU)	Data source (Ireland)	Data source (Germany)	Data source (Norway)	Data source (Czech)
Cropland	Crop production	Eurostat, 2023a	Eurostat, 2023a	Eurostat, 2023a	Eurostat, 2023a	Eurostat, 2023a
	Variable costs	Eurostat, 2023c; Eurostat, 2023d	Collins and Phelan, 2022	KTBL, 2023a	Eurostat, 2023c; Eurostat, 2023d	Eurostat, 2023c; Eurostat, 2023d
	Outputs and profit	Eurostat, 2023b	Collins and Phelan, 2022	KTBL, 2023a	Project partners; Eurostat, 2023b	
	Tillage practices	Hickey, 2013, Forristal and Murphy, 2009	FCI, 2022	KTBL, 2023b	Hickey, 2013, Forristal and Murphy, 2009	Hickey, 2013, Forristal and Murphy, 2009
	Tillage practices impact on crop protection	Chapelle-Barry (2008)	Chapelle-Barry (2008)	Chapelle-Barry (2008)	Chapelle-Barry (2008)	Chapelle-Barry (2008)
	Effect of cover crops on N fertiliser	Notz et al., 2023; Buckley et al., 2020	Notz et al., 2023; Buckley et al., 2020	Notz et al., 2023; Buckley et al., 2020	Notz et al., 2023; Buckley et al., 2020	Notz et al., 2023; Buckley et al., 2020
	Biochar effect on yields	Ye et al. (2019)	Ye et al. (2019)	Ye et al. (2019)	Ye et al. (2019)	Ye et al. (2019)
Irrigation costs	Borsato et al., 2019	Borsato et al., 2019	Borsato et al., 2019	Borsato et al., 2019	Borsato et al., 2019	
Grassland	Seed	Eurostat, 2023d	Dairygold, 2023a, b; Seeddirect, 2023	KTBL, 2023a	Project partners	Project partners
	Fertiliser price	Eurostat, 2023c	Collins and Phelan, 2022	Thünen data	Project partners	Project partners
	Fertiliser requirements	IFA	Hennessy et al., 2022	IFA	IFA	IFA
	Machinery		FCI, 2022	KTBL, 2023b		
	Profit		Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, 2022	KTBL, 2023a		
Agroforestry	Afforestation	Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	Vanessa Schulz et al. (2020)	Project partners	Project partners

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Maintenance	Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	Vanessa Schulz et al. (2020)	Project partners	Project partners
Good inputs	Eurostat, 2023e; Eurostat, 2021				

Table 2: Key assumptions for crop, grass and forestry requirements

Requirement	EU Value and Source	Ireland Value and Source	Germany Value and Source	Norway Value and Source	Czech Value and Source
Inflation rate from 2020 to 2022	14.02% Eurostat, 2023f	10.67% Eurostat, 2023f	12.19% Eurostat, 2023f	4.62% Project partner	18.6% Eurostat, 2023f
Inflation rate from 2020 to 2022 for diesel		48.97% Eurostat, 2023f	73.16% Eurostat, 2023f		
Deflation rate from 2023 to 2022		-3.1% Eurostat, 2023i	-4.14% Eurostat, 2023i		
Labour rate	€ 6.01 / hour Eurostat, 2023h	€ 10.5 / hour Irish DETE, 2021	€ 9.93 / hour Eurostat, 2023e	€ 16.32 / hour Project partner	€ 3.73 / hour Eurostat, 2023e
Nitrogen fertiliser price (average urea and CAN)	€ 1.7 / kg Eurostat, 2023c	€ 2.65 / kg Data.gov.ie, 2023	€ 1.42 / kg Agrarshop, 2023b	€ 1.40 / kg Project partner	€ 1.7 / kg
Carbon price	€ 89 / T CO ₂ World Bank, 2023	€ 49 / T CO ₂ World Bank, 2023	€ 30 / T CO ₂ World Bank, 2023	€ 96.3 / T CO ₂ Statistita, 2024	€ 57 / T CO ₂ World Bank, 2023
Diesel price	€ 1.42 / L Eurostat, 2023c	€ 1.89 / L Statistita, 2023	€ 1.54 / L Eurostat, 2023f	€ 1.17 / L Project partner	€ 1.6 / L Project partner
Biochar application rate	30 T. HA ⁻¹ Ye et al. (2019)	30 T. HA ⁻¹ Ye et al. (2019)	30 T. HA ⁻¹ Ye et al. (2019)	30 T. HA ⁻¹ Ye et al. (2019)	30 T. HA ⁻¹ Ye et al. (2019)
Water requirements for sprinkler irrigation	20 mm. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	20 mm. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	20 mm. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	20 mm. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	20 mm. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019
Labour requirements for sprinkler irrigation	5 hours. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	5 hours. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	5 hours. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	5 hours. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	5 hours. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019
Fuel requirements for sprinkler irrigation	263 L. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	263 L. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	263 L. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	263 L. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019	263 L. HA ⁻¹ Borsato et al., 2019
Good inputs for forestry activities	€ 109 / HA Eurostat, 2023e; Eurostat, 2021				€ 350 / HA Eurostat, 2023e; Eurostat, 2021
Materials and fuel for afforestation		€ 2872 / HA Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	€ 1035 / HA Project partner	€ 947 / HA Project partner	

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Total labour cost for afforestation	€ 702 / HA Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	€ 1002 / HA Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022	€ 738 / HA Project partner	€ 493 / HA Project partner	€ 436 / HA Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022
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Specific Assumptions

1. Technical Solution

1.1 Tillage

We consider two scenarios: The business as usual scenario where cropland is regularly tilled and inverted (IT) versus a) cropland that is undergoing reduced tillage (RT) and b) cropland that is undergoing zero tillage (ZT).

1.1.1 Zero-tillage

For this measure, crops are directly sown into the soil, and the soil is never tilled throughout the crop rotation.

The costs associated with implementing the ZT measure are the additional crop protection costs due to the proliferation of pests and diseases when the soil is not tilled. Pittelkow et al. (2015) performed a global meta-analysis on the effects of no-tillage on yields and found that, on average, across 50 crops, yields were reduced by 5.1% under no-tillage. We assume crop yields are then reduced by the same proportion under IT to ZT and 2.5% for RT to ZT. Chapelle-Barry (2008) found that farms under ZT had 25% higher crop protection costs (Eurostat, 2023d; Teagasc, 2022). Hence, this was applied to the cost base here.

The benefits of implementing the ZT measure are lower machinery, fuel and labour costs (vs inversion or min-till). We assume inversion tillage corresponds to “plough and one pass” and minimum tillage to “min-till / strip-till drill” in the FCI’s cost guidelines (2022).

Implementing the ZT measure offers benefits such as reduced machinery depreciation, fuel costs, and labour expenses. Fuel requirements for tillage operations are based on Teagasc advisory guidelines (Hickey, 2013), while labour requirements for both ploughing and minimum tillage are drawn from Forristal and Murphy (2009).

1.1.2 Non-inversion tillage / Reduced tillage

The measure involves tillage but no soil inversion throughout the crop rotation. The costs associated with implementing the RT measure are the additional crop protection costs due to the proliferation of

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pests and diseases when the soil is not inverted. There are some cost savings (machinery, fuel, labour) due to not ploughing. Pittelkow et al. (2015) performed a global meta-analysis on the effects of ZT on yields and found that, on average, across 50 crops, yields were reduced by 5.1% under ZT. To avoid underestimating the measure's costs, we assume crop yields are also reduced by 2.5% for RT. Chapelle-Barry (2008) found that farms with ZT has 25% higher crop protection costs versus the business as usual scenario. We then assume the original crop protection cost is multiplied by this factor. The benefits associated with implementing the minimum tillage measure are lower fuel and labour costs.

1.2 Biochar

The business as usual scenario, is agricultural land without biochar. We distinguish between biochar application on cropland (CL) and on grassland (GL). Ye et al. (2019) found that biochar application for continental and humid-temperate regions resulted in either a yield effect close to 0% or an insignificant yield effect overall. Hence, we do not consider any yield effects around biochar application.

We used the average market price of biochar in EU countries, and assume the soil organic carbon from biochar will be retained for 100 years (Leifeld et al., 2024, Hagemann et al., 2024). We also consider the contractor rate for biochar application in the case of cropland.

For grassland, it is assumed the biochar will be applied using slurry-spreading machinery at the same time as the slurry. For cropland, we take the fuel requirement for one pass from Teagasc advisory work (Hickey, 2013) and the labour requirements from Forristal and Murphy (2009).

1.3 Irrigation

The business as usual scenario is rain-fed cropland. We assume infrastructure and storage capacity related to irrigation already exist. We do not compute the additional costs related to fertiliser and crop protection requirements under irrigation compared to those under rain-fed crops as they are very difficult to quantify. As a follow-up to Emde et al. (2021), this study considers only sprinkler irrigation.

The main costs associated with irrigation are the labour and maintenance costs related to the infrastructure, as well as the energy and fuel costs. The sprinkler system requires fuel; the benefit associated with irrigation is the increase in yields for the affected crops, representing a revenue gain. Yield increases are taken from Teagasc (2017).

2 Crop Rotation

2.1 Cover crops

The business as usual scenario is cropland with partially bare soil for a period of the year. Under this cover crop scenario we now include one plant cover in the crop rotation on the cropland that was initially bare. To choose which cover crop to use for a given country, we take the crop that is the most present in terms of area cultivated amongst the cover crops used by Notz et al. (2023) (e.g. field peas, faba beans, common beans, lupin, soybean). For the EU-27 in 2022, this would be soya beans (Eurostat, 2023a). Outside of the carbon sequestration function, this measure also has the potential to increase biodiversity, increase nitrogen availability, decrease erosion risks and improve the soil structure.

Under this scenario it is assumed that the cover crop is not harvested, the harvesting costs are deducted from the variable costs. The costs associated with the implementation of the cover crop measure include the costs for seeds, fertilisers, and the fuel and labour costs associated with ploughing, tilling, sowing, fertiliser spraying and harvesting. The original fertiliser requirements were taken from the IFA (2022). We approximate the seed requirements of soy using requirements for oilseed rape as they are both oil crops. Seed requirements were taken from Teagasc (2022).

The benefits associated with the implementation of the measure are the cost savings due to the reduced N fertiliser requirements of subsequent crops. Notz et al. (2023) found that cropping systems including soybeans experienced a reduction of the N fertiliser use of 28% on average³. We assume the N fertiliser reduction will only happen in the year following the implementation of the measure.

2.2 Perennial legumes and temporary ley management

The business as usual scenario is a cropland without the incorporation of perennial legumes in the crop rotation cycle. The new scenario involves an incorporation of perennial legumes in rotation with crops (wheat, barley, oats, potatoes, oilseed rape) originally cultivated. A white clover-grass mixture is proposed as the legume used. Non-harvested forage legumes increase soil organic carbon in soils.

³ Average across 11 study areas across central east Europe, central west Europe and southern Europe.

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Therefore, it is also assumed that the legume will not be harvested but ploughed back into the soil before the subsequent crops are sown.

The costs associated with implementing this measure are the costs for seeds, fertiliser, machinery, fuel and labour. There is also an opportunity cost associated with not selling the original crop (wheat, barley, oats, potatoes, oilseed rape, maize) and the related straw. We assume no fertiliser is needed because the legumes are not being harvested. Since the legume mix is not harvested but ploughed back in the soil, we consider ploughing costs every year.

The seed costs for white clover are taken from the seed supplier Tuinzaden (2023b). We use the price of *White Clover Seeds 100M2 Green Manure*. The fertiliser requirements for the legume is taken from the IFA (2022) data on fertiliser usage on grassland. To evaluate the profit/loss from not selling the original crop, we used the yield and price of each crop from Eurostat (2023a; 2023b).

The benefits of implementing this measure stem primarily from cost savings associated with eliminating the variable cost of producing the original crops. For instance, since white clover is not harvested but rather ploughed back into the soil, there are additional fuel savings from not harvesting the original crop, while ploughing costs remain consistent between the original crops and white clover. Furthermore, no fertiliser is applied to the clover as it will not be harvested, resulting in further cost savings by avoiding the use of machinery for fertilisation and harvesting operations.

A key advantage of incorporating clover lies in its ability to fix nitrogen, reducing the nitrogen fertiliser requirements for subsequent crops in the rotation. According to Buckley et al. (2020), white clover can fix between 80 and 200 kg of nitrogen per hectare, which translates into an equivalent reduction in nitrogen fertiliser use for the following crops. For this analysis, the midpoint of this range—140 kg of nitrogen per hectare—is used and adjusted for the length of the growing period. This fertiliser saving is assumed to occur one year after the measure is implemented, contributing to significant cost reductions in subsequent crop cycles.

2.3 Crop residue management

The business as usual scenario is cropland, where crop by-products such as straw is removed without return. Under this scenario, the straw and other crop residues are assumed to be left in the field and ploughed back into the soil.

The cost associated with implementing this measure is an opportunity cost due to the straw not being sold. Nicholson et al. (2014) found that straw incorporation did not significantly affect weeds, diseases,

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pests and crop establishment. Hence, there is no additional crop protection costs. The straw price was taken from Eurostat (2023c) and straw yields from Caslin (2020).

3. Woody Vegetation

3.1 Silvopasture

The business as usual scenario is pasture without trees (grassland without silvopasture). The measure integrates trees, forage and grazing on the same land. It is assumed the biomass from the trees is not harvested and that 10% of a hectare of land will be covered with trees.

The costs of silvopasture implementation are labour and machinery costs, the costs associated with materials and fuel, and the administrative costs (such as licencing costs) induced by tree planting. The cost associated with goods needed for tree planting is taken from Eurostat (2023e; 2021). Labour requirements associated with tree planting are taken from the COFORD Council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) report (Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022).

Since it is assumed that the trees will not be harvested, harvesting costs are not considered. We assume the cost of afforestation will only occur in year 1 when the measure is implemented (but this is discounted over 25 years), but we presume maintenance costs occur every year. There is no benefit associated with the biomass from trees since it is assumed they are not harvested.

3.2 Alley-Cropping

The business as usual scenario is cropland without agroforestry. The measure involves planting trees on cropland, forming lines and covering between 10 and 15% of the cropland area. The trees are grown for at least 25 years before being harvested. Outside of the carbon sequestration, the environmental benefits of the measure include increased biodiversity and reduced erosion and nitrogen leaching.

The costs associated with agroforestry are labour and machinery costs, materials and fuel, and the capital costs induced by tree planting. There is an opportunity cost as the original crops area is not available. The costs of implementation for trees are taken from the COFORD Council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) report on the economics of the forest sector in Ireland (Forestry Services Ltd. And Phillips, 2022).

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We consider an average between the three species considered in the report (conifer, broad leaves hard and broad leaves soft). Since it is assumed that the trees will not be harvested, harvesting costs are not considered. We assume the cost of afforestation will only occur in year 1 when the measure is implemented, but we presume maintenance costs arise every year. The material inputs for forestry activities are taken from Eurostat (2023e). The benefits of this measure are the variable costs associated to the original crops that will not be spent.

3.3 Hedges

In terms of the business as usual scenario here relates to a) cropland used for annual crop (CL) b) grassland (GL). The potential co-benefits associated with the measure outside of carbon storage are similar to those mentioned for silvopasture. It is assumed the biomass from hedges is not harvested.

Similar to the other woody vegetation and due to lack of available EU wide data. We use Eurostat (2023e) for forestry good inputs and the COFORD council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) report (Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022) for labour requirements. From the report, we only consider broad leaves and soft leaves, as we assume conifers will not be used as hedgerows⁴. Since it is assumed that the hedges will not be harvested, harvesting costs are not considered.

The opportunity costs for not producing the original crop (cereals or grass) are taken from Eurostat (2023a; 2023b). The benefits associated to this measure are similar to alleycropping and silvopasture which include reduced cost of seed, fertilizer, fuel labour and machinery. Since it is believed that the hedgerows will not be harvested, harvesting costs are not considered. We assume the cost of hedgerow establishment will only occur in year 1 when the measure is implemented, but we assume maintenance costs arise every year.

⁴ Where country specific data are available for hedges (such as whitelorn and blacklorn) for instance Ireland and Germany, the data was used to estimate the cost of hedge planting and hedge maintenance. See Appendix for details

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Part V- Result of the Cost of Abatement

The costs associated with implementing these measures, which can result in either a positive cost or a negative cost (benefit), are estimated at both a per hectare farm level (€) and the aggregate EU (or country level - € million) based on relevant areas it could be implemented.

Table 3 provides an overview of the average net costs of implementing various mitigation measures across the EU on a per hectares and aggregate basis.

Table 3: Overview of the selected carbon (C) accrual measures and their cost of implementation for the EU

Measure	Area of Implementation ('000 hectares)	Farm-level Cost of Implementation (€ ha ⁻¹)	Aggregate cost of Implementation (€'million)
Silvopasture	1,470	188	276
Hedges on grassland	1,470	193	284
Alley-Cropping	1,470	299	439
Hedges on cropland	1,470	301	442
Perennial legumes	5,459	254	1,386
Crop Residues	11,597	148	1,715
Irrigation	13,395	139	1,863
Min till to Zero Till	42,174	66	2,804
IT - ZT	42,174	92	3,867
Cover crops	19,557	218	4,254
IT-RT	87,778	62	5,413
Biochar grassland	28,055	936	26,248
Biochar cropland	28,055	936	26,269

Farm level (per hectare) and country levels cost of abatement are shown in Tables 5 and 6 respectively (area of implementation is also shown in Table 4). Results indicate that costs varies significantly between the farm and country levels.

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Table 4: Area of implementation ('000 hectares) for selected carbon sequestration measures by country

Agricultural measure	Technical solutions						Crop rotations			Woody vegetation				
	Tillage			Biochar			Irrigation	Cover crops	Crop Residues	Perennial legumes	Hedges on grassland	Hedges on cropland	Silvopasture	Alley-Cropping
	IT to RT	IT to ZT	RT to ZT	Biochar grassland	Biochar cropland									
Czech	1845	833	833	922	922	66	384	0	254	38	38	38	38	
Germany	6824	3217	3217	3786	3786	351	2174	0	1906	124	124	124	124	
Ireland	255	126	126	220	24	0	7	0	6	11	11	11	11	
Norway	172	82	82	82	82	121	6	0	0	5	5	5	5	

Table 5: Cost per hectare (€ ha⁻¹) of selected carbon sequestration measures by country

Agricultural measure	Technical solutions						Crop rotations			Woody vegetation				
	Tillage			Biochar			Irrigation	Cover crops	Crop Residues	Perennial legumes	Hedges on grassland	Hedges on cropland	Silvopasture	Alley-Cropping
	IT to RT	IT to ZT	RT to ZT	Biochar grassland	Biochar cropland									
Czech	55	77	60	525	525	199	185	117	207	285	374	284	373	
Germany	23	99	99	135	137	178	313	301	291	3762	3919	1944	2137	
Ireland	33	58	62	345	345	274	466	145	177	160	217	397	450	
Norway	23	44	32	222	222	147	106	160	190	240	498	326	438	

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Table 6: Country-level cost of implementation (€'million) of selected carbon sequestration measures by country

Agricultural measure	Technical solutions						Crop rotations			Woody vegetation				
	Tillage			Biochar			Irrigation	Cover crops	Crop Residues	Perennial legumes	Hedges on grassland	Hedges on cropland	Silvopasture	Alley-Cropping
	IT to RT	IT to ZT	RT to ZT	Biochar grassland	Biochar cropland									
Czech	102	64	50	484	484	13	71	0	53	11	14	11	14	
Germany	159	318	319	511	520	62	682	0	555	465	484	240	264	
Ireland	8	7	8	76	8	0	3	0	1	2	2	4	5	
Norway	4	4	3	18	18	18	1	0	0	1	2	1	2	

Part VI- Calculation of the cost-effectiveness and Construction the MACC curve

1. Estimation of the cost-effectiveness of a measure

The cost-effectiveness of a measure shows the ratio of the cost of abatement to the carbon sequestration potential. Measures could either have a negative value, implying that the measure sequesters carbon and leads to monetary savings. Alternatively, a positive value implies that although the measure sequesters carbon, it has some monetary cost implications (Buckley et al., 2020; Lanigan et al., 2023; Ogunpaimo et al., 2024). Mathematically, the cost-effectiveness of a measure is represented as

$$CE_i = \frac{COA_i (\text{€})}{CSP_i (\text{MgCO}_2\text{e sequestered})} \quad (4)$$

Where

CE is the cost-effectiveness of a mitigation measure i

COA is the cost of abatement of a mitigation measure i

CSP is the carbon sequestration potential mitigation measure i.

It is noteworthy that the formula in equation 4 represents the cost-effectiveness of a mitigation measure at the farm level. At the aggregate or country level analysis, the cost-effectiveness i represented as

$$CE_i = \frac{COA_i (\text{€'million})}{CSP_i (\text{MioMgCO}_2\text{e sequestered})} \quad (5)$$

The cost effectiveness of a mitigation measures tends to be measures against some benchmark. In this case the benchmark related to the shadow price of carbon. The shadow price in this instance is € 89 / Mg CO₂ per mega gram of CO₂e for the EU taken from (World Bank, 2023).

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2. Results of the Cost-effectiveness of Mitigation Measures on the Farm-level and Aggregate Scale

The cost-effectiveness result (EU scale) are presented in Table 7 (per hectare) and Table 8 (aggregate). As indicated, it can be observed that although all the measures are cost-positive at the farm and the national level for the EU, the rankings of measures range from being cost-effective to cost-prohibited based on the shadow price of carbon of € 89 / Mg CO_{2e}. For instance, woody vegetation measures such as hedgerows and silvopasture are cost-effective, while others (like cover crops) may be classified as not currently cost-effective based on the prevailing shadow price of carbon as shown in Table 7. As shown in Tables 7 & 8, despite the varying levels of abatement potential and the cost of implementation, the cost-effectiveness at the farm level and aggregate level are the same due to the relative numerator and denominator.

Table 7: Farm-level cost-effectiveness of selected measures for the EU

Measure	Farm-level cost (€ ha ⁻¹)	Carbon Sequestration potential (Mg CO ₂ e)	Cost Effectiveness (€ per Mg CO ₂ e)
Silvopasture	188	7.2	26
Hedges on grassland	193	7.2	27
Alley-Cropping	299	7.2	41
Hedges on cropland	301	7.2	42
Biochar grassland	234	1.4	170
Biochar cropland	234	1.4	171
Min till to Zero Till	66	0.4	178
Perennial legumes	254	1.3	192
Crop Residues	148	0.8	196
IT to ZT	92	0.4	246
IT to RT	62	0.1	604
Irrigation	139	0.2	666
Cover crops	218	0.2	1023

Shadow price of carbon
€89 / Mg CO_{2e}

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Table 8: Aggregate-level cost-effectiveness of selected measures for the EU

Measure	Area of implementation ('000 ha)	Aggregate cost (€'million)	Mio Mg CO ₂ e	Cost Effectiveness (€ per Mg CO ₂ e)
Silvopasture	1470	276	11	26
Hedges on grassland	1470	284	11	27
Alley-Cropping	1470	439	11	41
Hedges on cropland	1470	442	11	42
Biochar grassland	28055	6562	39	170
Biochar cropland	28055	6567	39	171
Min till to Zero Till	42174	2804	16	178
Perennial legumes	5459	1386	7	192
Crop Residues	11597	1715	9	196
IT to ZT	42174	3867	16	246
IT to RT	87778	5413	9	604
Irrigation	13395	1863	3	666
Cover crops	19557	4254	4	1023

The ranking of measures also varies across the different countries; where a measure is cost-effective in one country, it might be cost-prohibited in another, or be ranked highly in one country and lowly in another. For example, land use change from pasture to silvopasture, despite being cost-effective in the EU and the Czech Republic, is cost-prohibited in Ireland. Also, it is noteworthy that some measures implemented at the European scale (or in some countries) are not applicable in other countries, and as such, cost-effectiveness is not present in the countries where they are not implemented. For instance, irrigation facilities are not relevant in Ireland, however the measures are applicable at German and European levels. As shown in Table 9, despite the varying levels of abatement potential and the cost of implementation, the cost-effectiveness at the farm level and aggregate level are the same due to the relative numerator and denominator.

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Table 9: Cost effectiveness of selected measures for different countries in € Mg CO₂e⁻¹

Agricultural measure	Technical solutions						Crop rotations			Woody vegetation				
	Tillage			Biochar			Irrigation	Cover crops	Crop Residues	Perennial legumes	Hedges on grassland	Hedges on cropland	Silvopasture	Alley-Cropping
	IT to RT	IT to ZT	RT to ZT	Biochar grassland	Biochar cropland									
Czech	510	188	147	382	383	657	890		155	39	52	39	52	
Germany	189	221	222	98	100	779	1262	0	215	512	534	265	291	
Ireland	211	92	99	255	257		185		56	23	31	57	65	
Norway	0	0	0	159	159	445	33	0	0	31	65	43	57	

3. MACC at the Farm-level and Aggregate scale

As set out by Lanigan et al. (2018) a marginal abatement cost curve (MACC) is a graph that visualises the abatement potential of a number of mitigation measures as well as the relative costs associated with each of these measures. Visually a MACC provides two important data elements.

Firstly, the width of the bar on the graph indicates the magnitude of the abatement potential of each individual measure. Secondly it ranks (left to right) the mitigation measures from high to low in terms of the cost-effectiveness.

In addition, a MACC generally includes an indication of the price of carbon credits on the international market (i.e. shadow price of carbon). Cost-beneficial measures are measures that fall below the X axis (sequester carbon and reduce cost), cost-neutral measures are measures that sequester carbon but have zero cost (these are on the X axis). Cost effective measures are those that incur a cost but this cost is below the shadow price of carbon (above the X axis but below carbon price line) and cost prohibitive measures are those that sequester carbon but are incur a cost above the shadow price of carbon (above the X axis and carbon price line).

The MACC at EU scale is illustrated in Figure 1 (aggregate) and Figure 2 (farm level per hectare scale), with measures ranked from cost-beneficial to cost-prohibitive measures. At the shadow carbon price of €89 Mg CO₂e⁻¹ for the EU, woody vegetation measures (silvopasture, alley cropping and hedges on cropland and on grassland) are the only cost-effective measures. No measures were deemed cost beneficial or cost-neutral. Hence, most of the measures considered are currently not cost-effective to implement at the current carbon price despite their ability to sequester carbon.

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Fig. 1 shows the Aggregate-level MACC for the EU.

Fig. 2 shows the Farm-level MACC for the EU

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Appendix

Table A1. Table showing the country specific assumptions

Measure	Ireland	Germany	Other Countries
General	<p>Prices for tillage-related practices were taken from Farm Contractors Ireland (FCI, 2022).</p> <p>Prices include a value-added tax of 13.5%, fuel use, machinery and labour costs.</p> <p>For nitrogen fertiliser price, we use an average between Urea (46% N) and CAN (27.5% N) prices (Data.gov.ie, 2023). The carbon price in Ireland changed on May 1st, 2022. We take the weighted average between the price from January 1st, 2022 to April 30th, 2022, and from May 1st 2022 to December 31st, 2022 (Revenue, 2023).</p> <p>For arable management practices, we use Teagasc's <i>Crop Costs and Returns</i> booklet, which is a guide for best practices related to crop production in Ireland (Collins and Phelan, 2022). The booklet breaks down variable costs (seed, fertilisers, sprays, hire machinery, miscellaneous) and return (profit based on a target yield) for the main crops produced in Ireland.</p> <p>For profits related to cereal straws, the Irish Straw Incorporation Measure (SIM) 's payment is used as a proxy for straw price. For each crop where both are presented, we take an average between the spring and the winter species. The prices consider CAN + S prices from the beginning of the year 2022. To account for the surge in prices observed after the start of the war in Ukraine in March 2022, we recalculated the fertiliser costs using the average price between Urea and CAN.</p> <p>Seed costs and rate of application are taken from two primary seed providers in Ireland, Dairygold (2023a) for the lower-bound cost and Seeddirect (2023) for the upper-bound cost.</p> <p>For measures including agroforestry (alley cropping, silvopasture, hedges), the costs of implementation for trees/hedgerows are taken from the COFORD</p>	<p>Data on variable cost of pasture was taken from KTBL website.</p> <p>For tillage-related management practices, we use the costs, returns, and gross margin computed by the <i>Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft</i> (KTBL), <i>Standarddeckungsbeiträge</i> (2023a).</p> <p>All other assumptions follow from the EU</p>	<p>Follows from the assumption for the EU.</p>

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Council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) 's report on the economics of the forest sector in Ireland (Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022). The report is based on 2020 activity levels, so prices are corrected for inflation.

Table A1. Table showing the country specific assumptions

Measure	Ireland	Germany	Other Countries
Tillage	We assume inversion tillage corresponds to “plough and one pass” and minimum tillage to “min-till / strip-till drill” in the FCI’s cost guidelines (2022).	We assume inversion tillage corresponds to “Pflügen mit Drehverstellpflug (2 Schare, 67 kW)” and minimum tillage to “Grubber” https://www.forstpraxis.de/sites/forstpraxis.de/files/2023-07/AFZ_FHJ_Kalender_2024_222_225_Bestandesbegr%C3%BCndung_ste.pdf	Follows from the assumption for the EU.
Cover crop	The main cost associated with the implementation of the cover crop measure in Ireland is the variable costs associated with beans production. For Ireland in 2022, this would be field beans (Eurostat, 2023a)	For Germany the most dominant cover crops is soya beans (Eurostat, 2023a)	Follows from the assumption for the EU.
Perennial legumes	Seed costs and rate of application are taken from two primary seed providers in Ireland, Dairygold (2023a) for the lower-bound cost and Seeddirekt (2023) for the upper-bound cost. Dairygold proposes an acre pack composed of a grass mixture including white clover (Gold Assure No.3 +EXTEND Gold Grass Seed - Acre Pack With Clover) priced at €76. Seeddirekt proposes an acre pack composed of a grass mixture including white clover (MULTI SPECIES (X6) DAFM SPEC.) priced at €99. We average those two mixes for a representative price of €85 per acre, so €209 per hectare in 2022.	The price of clover seeds is taken from Agrarshop (2023a). All other assumptions follow from the EU assumptions	Price of white clover were provided by project partners from the countries

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Crop Residues	The implementation costs are taken from the FCI (2022). The opportunity cost is taken from Collins and Phelan (2022). The total straw price was taken from Collins, and Phelan (2022)		Follows from the assumption for the EU were applicable
Biochar	For land with cropland, it is assumed the biochar will be applied using muck spreading, we use the price of Muck Spreading – 10 tonnes from the FCI rates.	For cropland, we use the price of <i>Gülle Verschlauchung ab Zubringer mit Transport, Güllegrubber</i> from the KTBL (2023b) rates.	Follows from the assumption for the EU.

Table A1. Table showing the country specific assumptions

Measure	Ireland	Germany	Other Countries
Silvopasture	<p>The costs of implementation for trees are taken from the COFORD Council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) ’s report on the economics of the forest sector in Ireland (Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022).</p> <p>To quantify the benefits from grass production, we use the pasture profit index (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, 2022) of each species in the grass mix considered for seeds (see grass mixes assumed for original grassland below). The average for each mix is weighted by the relative importance of the species in the mix. We then take an average of both mixes mentioned above.</p> <p>Similar to other measures involving grass production, the seed cost is taken from one of the main suppliers in Ireland (Dairygold, 2023b). We take an average price between their cheaper acre bag of grass mixture (<i>Gold Assure No. 2 Two Cut Silage Grass Seed (No Clover) - Acre Pack</i>) and their most expensive one (<i>Gold Assure No.3 +EXTEND Gold Grass Seed - Acre Pack With Clover</i>). This gives an average price of €67 per acre and €165 per hectare in 2022 prices.</p> <p>The implementation costs for grass are taken from the FCI (2022). Teagasc (2022) advises a fertiliser rate of 90 kg per hectare for grass mixtures. The opportunity cost is obtained from Collins and Phelan (2022). If the crop is not harvested, the harvesting costs are deducted from the variable costs. We also consider that the grass will not be fertilised so we discard the fertiliser costs. We assume the grass mixture is reseeded every 10 years. Hence, we assume the cost of full ploughing in year 0, and minimum tillage costs for the rest of the 25-year period.</p> <p>We consider an average between the three species considered in the report (conifer, broad leaves hard and broad leaves soft).</p>	<p>The assumptions follow from Ireland and in addition data on forestry activities are obtained from Thunen (https://agroforst-info.de/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Agroforst-Systeme_Leitfaden.pdf).</p> <p>Similar to other measures involving grass production, for the grass costs and benefits, we use the gross margin for pasture from the KTBL gross margin calculator (KTBL, 2023a).</p>	Follows from the assumption for the EU.

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Alley cropping	<p>Similar to previous measures involving crop production, the profits from the original crops and straw that are lost due to the replacement of the cropland by agroforestry are obtained from Teagasc’s Crop Costs and Returns report (Collins and Phelan, 2022).</p>	<p>Similar to Ireland, the variable costs for original crop production are obtained from ktbl website (https://daten.ktbl.de/sdb/source.do)</p>
Hedges	<p>For cropland, similar to previous measures involving crop production, the profits from the original crops and straw that are lost due to the replacement of the cropland by woody vegetation are obtained from Teagasc’s Crop Costs and Returns report (Collins and Phelan, 2022).</p> <p>The costs of implementation for hedgerows are taken from the COFORD Council (Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine) ’s report on the economics of the forest sector in Ireland (Forestry Services Ltd. and Phillips, 2022).</p>	<p>Data on hedge establishment and maintenance were taken from Thünen, including 2 offers by companies (in german)</p>
